

The Effects of Rural Labour Migration Process on Occupational Distribution, Family Facilities and Livelihoods

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Abstract— Migration of human beings is a phenomenon which has historical roots and wider implications. Migrations have economic genesis but resulting socio-political cultural ramifications. In economic parlance, migration is perceived as when a person is engaged or likely to engage in a remunerative activity in a place of which he is not a native or national. The migrants send remittances to their relatives in the rural areas and these remittance-receiving households use the remittances for various purposes. With this background keeping in mind the present study was conducted with some objectives, such as, to recognize the changing pattern of occupational scenario of the study area; to identify the changes of family facilities before and after migration and to compare the income differences before and after migration. The study was conducted on 100 numbers of respondents in three villages named Chengerkuthi Khalisamari, Jatamari, and Choto Khalisamari under Khalisamari Gram Panchayat of Coochbehar district of West Bengal. The statistical method used for analysis and interpretation of raw data were mean, frequency percentage and paired 't' test. It is noticeable due to high remunerative and regularity of income, the youth and middle aged group are more attracted for migration. The study also reveals migration process transformed the occupational distribution of the respondents massively. The income variation factor before and after migration are also in favour of migration. It is evident that after migration the family daily life standard changed towards a positive direction. The number of cell phone users and bank account holder also increased.

Keywords— Family daily life standard, Migration, Per-capita income, Rural Labour.

I. INTRODUCTION

Migration is the intrinsic character of rural livelihood of India. Many a time, the low economic productivity of the small and fragmented holding associated with uncertainty and seasonality of market prices accrued to the farmers have steered to the process of migration from their own village to elsewhere in search of economic and social security as well. Migration is shift from a place of residence to another place for some length of time or permanently including different types of voluntary movements. It has great impact on economic, social, cultural and psychological life of people, both at place of emigration as well as of migration (Kaur, 2003). Migration of workers is a human phenomenon which has historical roots and wider implications. The search for the source of survival or quest for Eldorado, the blissful life, has ever remained the inspiring and the dovetailing force of migrations. Migrations have economic genesis but resulting socio-political cultural ramifications. Indeed, mingling of different cultures has had positive consequences as well as placing strain on the culture and life of the upcoming society affected in either way by migration. In economic parlance, migration is perceived as when a person is engaged or likely to engage in a remunerative activity in a place of which he is not a native or national.

Migration is an important feature of human civilization. It reflects, human endeavour to survive in the most testing conditions both natural and man-made. Migration in India has existed historically, but, in the context of globalization and opening up of the world economy it has assumed special significance for the country and the society. As a consequence of historical and economic factors, there are serious income disparities, agrarian distress, inadequate employment generation, vast growth of informal economy and the resultant migration from rural areas to urban, urban to urban and backward to comparatively advanced regions in the most appalling conditions. Migration is a global phenomenon. Uneven economic development, inter-regional disparity and differences in living standards between socio-economic groups are some of the important reasons responsible for migration.

The last few decades have observed massive seasonal or permanent migration of peasants from rural to urban areas in the third world countries. This has been extensively documented, and there has also been an enormous growth of theoretical literature and empirical evidence towards an understanding of the realities of rural-urban migration. The phenomenon has also led to a considerable debate on the process of capitalist penetration into rural areas and its role in influencing the existing

socio-economic differentiation in the countryside. One of the prominent theoretical arguments on rural-urban migration views it as individual utility maximization behaviour (Hariss and Todaro 1970), where wage differentials between the urban and rural sectors are considered to be the prime determinant of migration. The neoclassical expected income model of Todaro, with its numerous variants, seems to focus on individual potential migrants, and argues that holding much less constant; people will migrate if they expect to do better than they would if they did not move. The neoclassical theory of migration is largely based on the Lewis model, where the institutionally given urban wage rate and the wage differential between the urban and rural sectors form the basis of framework. This implies that migration from the rural to the urban sector results when the actual rural wage rate falls short of the expected urban wage rate. However, the neo-classical model, which is the most dominating framework in the context of rural-urban migration, assumes that rural migrants are a homogeneous category of poor people, ignoring the fact that their migration is not always based on a strategy of maximization, but of survival. The circulation of labour or migration from rural to urban areas is at times a response to economic necessity. Of land-owning and other institutional mechanisms that lead to migration from rural to urban areas.

The study on the effects of migration process on socio-economic status of the rural population has remained relevant since migration acts as a catalyst in the social transformation process. Migration process not only affects the destiny of individual migrants but also it has a great impact on the conditions of family members left behind, local communalities, social and cultural scenario. Trend of rural labour migration towards urban territory is mainly drive by the regularity of income, high remittances and perceived high social esteem. The migrants send remittances to their relatives in the rural areas and these remittance-receiving households use the remittances for various purposes. With this background keeping in mind the present study was conducted with some objectives, such as: to recognize the changing pattern of occupational scenario of the study area; to identify the changes of family facilities before and after migration; to compare the income differences before and after migration.

II. METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted in three villages named Chengerkuthi Khalisamari, Jatamari, and Choto Khalisamari under Khalisamari Gram Panchayat of Coochbehar district of West Bengal. For analysis of the socio-economic status of migrants household level the data was collected from the migrant individual as well as their family member also. Total number of respondent was 100. State, district, block, gram panchyate were selected purposively but villages and respondents were selected by simple random sampling method. Data collection was done through personal interview method with the help of structured schedule. The statistical method used for analysis and interpretation of raw data were mean, frequency percentage and paired ‘t’ test.

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

FIG. 1 OCCUPATIONAL DISTRIBUTION OF THE RESPONDENTS BEFORE MIGRATION

The above Fig. reveals the occupational distribution of the respondent before the migration. It represents that from the chart that 82 percent of the respondent was farmer, 11 percent were unemployed, and 7 percent were student.

FIG. 2 OCCUPATIONAL DISTRIBUTION OF THE RESPONDENTS AFTER MIGRATION

The Fig. shows the occupational pattern of the respondent after migration. It reveals from the chart that 3 percent of the respondent government services, 2 percent business, 11 percent in textile industry, 12 percent car driver, 7 percent house keeper, 19 percent industry labour, 5 percent in brick industry, 5 percent versatile job, in sweet shop 3 percent, in cloth shop 3 percent, in others stationary shops 4 percent, labour in stone industry 2 percent, 4 percent in tea garden, 4 percent van puller, 4 percent rickshaw puller, 6 percent stonemason, 3 percent repairing, 3 percent some non-governmental companies.

This study clearly indicates that there was a tremendous transformation on occupational distribution before and after migration. Rural economy is basically agriculture dominated. The increasing population rate causes decreasing land-human ratio which results unemployment as well as under employment situation in rural economy. Side by side the regular investment on agricultural sector and uncertainty regarding return also is an important characteristic of rural economy. The youth and middle age group of the rural population with comparatively high educational qualification and social exposure are losing their interest on farming sector and searching for a versatile job sector. Urban unorganised sector attract them with a lot of choice and comparatively regularity of income which influence the rural population to take part in migration process. As a results of this the occupational distribution which was previously (before migration) monolithic (dominated by agriculture) in nature totally changed into versatility after migration.

3.1 Change of family facilities before and after migration: a comparative study

**TABLE 1
CHANGE OF FAMILY FACILITIES BEFORE AND AFTER MIGRATION**

Change of family facilities before and after migration		
	Before Migration	After Migration
Good quality Water Facilities	15%	85%
Toilet Facilities	23%	77%
Cell Phone	15%	85%
Bank Account	4%	96%

FIGURE 1: CHANGE OF FAMILY FACILITIES BEFORE AND AFTER MIGRATION

The study reveals that, most of the respondents (85 percent) indicate their family enjoys the benefit of quality water facilities after migration, whereas only 15 percent respondent indicates that, they enjoy these facilities before migration. The study also reveals that 77 percent of respondent’s family gets the benefit of good sanitation facilities after migration, whereas only 23 percent of them indicate that they enjoy these facilities before migration. The remittance due to migration and regularity of income the migrant’s households can affords good quality water in daily life. It is also reveals that after migration process a major portion of respondents adopt the good sanitation facilities which help to live a healthy life. This phenomenon indicates migration has a positive impact on migrant’s standard of living.

It is also observed that before migration only 24 percent of migrants get the benefit of bank account whereas after the migration the 74 percent of respondent come under the benefit of the banking facilities. Before migration the respondents had no requirements for banking facilities but after migration for sending remittance, making transactions they come under the arena of banking sectors. The study reveals that before migration only 15 percent of migrants use cell phone in daily life whereas after migration 85 percent of the respondent started to use cell phone. Before migration the needs for communication, social exposure was less. After migration due to maintain the contacts, builds up communication network and other requirements the number of cell phone users increased.

3.2 Change in per-capita income before and after migration: a comparative study

**TABLE 2
PAIR ‘T’ TEST FOR COMPARING INCOME DIFFERENCES BEFORE AND AFTER MIGRATION**

Paired Samples Statistics									
		Mean	N	SD	Std. Error Mean				
Pair 1	A	4.704	100	1188.85685	118.88569				
	B	1.419	100	367.27085	36.72709				
Paired Samples Test									
		Paired Differences					t	df	Significance (2-tailed)
		Mean	SD	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
					Lower	Upper			
Pair 1	A- B	3.28	1296.0	129.602	3028.130	3542.450	25.34	99	0.000

Where, *A = per capita Income after Migration*
B = per capita Income before Migration

At 5 percent probability level and 99 degrees of freedom (N-1) where, N indicates total no. of respondents, the table t value is 1.984 and at 1 percent probability level and 99 degrees of freedom, the table t value is 2.626.

't' – test is used for comparing the means of two independent group .the t test was used to test the variation in per capita income before migration and after migration. It is observed that the calculated value of t was 25.349 which are highly significant at 5 percent level of significance (1.984) and also at 1 percent level of significance (2.626) hence, we can conclude that there is a significant difference in per capita income of all respondents before and after migration. This results clearly indicates that migration has a positive and significant impact on livelihood income generation and increment which influence the rural population to take part on the process.

IV. CONCLUSION

Human mobility in its many and varied forms, within and across national borders, is a major characteristic and perhaps even one of the defining features of our contemporary world. People move in ever increasing numbers and for many different purposes related to work, family, social, educational, cultural, business or personal safety concerns; sometimes within their own countries, at other times across the nearest border or perhaps across the world. It is noticeable due to high remunerative and regularity of income, the youth and middle age group are more attracted for migration. The study reveals that migration process transformed the occupational distribution of the migrants massively. The income variation factor before and after migration are in favour of migration also. The study also found that after migration the family daily life status changed towards a positive direction. The number of cell phone users and bank account holder also increased.

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